

Methoxy-Mercuration of α, β -Unsaturated Carbonyl Compounds

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The kinetics of methoxy-mercuration of methyl crotonate, crotonaldehyde and α -methyl cinnamaldehyde has been studied. The reaction shows pronounced acceleration in rate in the presence of perchloric acid. Acetic acid also exerts some accelerating effect, whereas sodium acetate and triethanolamine exert a strong retarding effect. The results indicate that an ionic mechanism presumably operates in the oxy-mercuration of α, β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds in general. Neither the relative rates nor the activation energy and the entropy of activation are, however, in conformity with what should be expected from structural considerations.

Oxymercuration of different types of unsaturated compounds are reported to involve two different mechanisms¹⁻⁷, one ionic and the other non-ionic. Further studies by Das *et al.* lead to the conclusion that methoxy-mercuration of acrylonitrile¹⁰ presumably proceeds by a non-ionic mechanism, whereas an ionic mechanism operates in the methoxymercuration of acrylic⁸, methacrylic and cinnamic esters as well as cinnamic aldehyde⁹.

The present paper reports the results of kinetic studies on the oxy-mercuration of some more olefins.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials :

Crotonaldehyde (trans) : The sample which was a B.D.H. (England) product of analytical reagent grade was twice distilled in an all glass apparatus under atmospheric pressure. The middle fraction having boiling point 102°–103° was collected and used for the kinetic studies.

Methyl crotonate (trans) : This was prepared by the method described in the literature¹¹ and was finally distilled; the middle fraction having boiling point 120°–121° was used.

α -methyl cinnamaldehyde : This was purified by the following procedure :

The sample was first washed with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution, then shaken with ether (A.R., B.D.H.) in a separating funnel. The ether layer after being taken out was distilled over a steam bath for complete removal of ether. The residue containing α -methyl cinnamaldehyde was subjected to distillation under reduced pressure in an all glass apparatus. The middle fraction having a constant boiling point was collected and used.

Reagent solutions were prepared and standardised as described earlier⁸⁻¹⁰, and experimental details for kinetic measurements were also the same.

The initial concentration of the olefinic compounds in the reaction mixtures were different for different compounds depending upon their reactivity. For crotonaldehyde the initial concentration was 0.005*M*–0.01*M*, for methyl crotonate it was 0.025*M*–0.05*M* whereas for α -methyl cinnamic aldehyde the concentration was 0.5 moles/litre. Mercuric acetate concentration was in the range 0.005*M*–0.025*M*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The reaction follows first-order kinetics with respect to each of the reactants. The order of reactivity of the olefins studied is :

Crotonaldehyde > methyl crotonate > α -methyl cinnamaldehyde. The compounds such as acrylamide, ethyl α -cyanocinnamate, trans-stilbene and benzalacetone show very little tendency to undergo methoxymercuration under the conditions employed.

The accelerating effect of the added acids and retarding effect of the bases (Tables 1 & 2) can be explained by reasonings similar to those adduced earlier^{8,9}, with the help of the ionic mechanism, as shown below :

The retarding effect of added acetate ion can easily be interpreted with the help of equation (1) as arising from a decrease in the steady state concentration of the reactive ion I. Nitrogen base brings about retardation presumably through the formation of coordination complexes with the reactive ion I, resulting in its deactivation.

In the presence of perchloric acid, the reaction presumably occurs via a different mechanism involving direct catalysis by hydrogen ions through the formation of a protonated complex. The accelerating effect may also arise indirectly as a result of the removal of acetate ions and consequent increase in the steady state or equilibrium concentration of the reactive intermediate I. In the presence of acetic acid, the accelerating effect of the hydrogen ions apparently out-weighs the retarding effect of the acetate ions formed by the dissociation, thus producing an overall acceleration.

Considering the relative rates of methoxy-mercuration of the α , β -unsaturated esters studied in the present as well as previous investigations^{8,9}, the following order is obtained :

crotonic > acrylic > cinnamic > methacrylic.

A methyl substituent on the β -carbon atom (in crotonic ester) appears to enhance the rate, as expected for an electrophilic reaction like the addition of mercuric acetate. But then

TABLE 1

Rate constants (k) for reaction between Mercuric acetate (a) and Crotonaldehyde (b) in methanol at different temperatures and in presence of added substances

$$a = 0.005M-0.01M$$

$$b = 0.005M-0.01M$$

Temperature °C	k lit.mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
10	0.90
15	1.22
20	1.55
30	2.00

Temperature $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$

Added substances with concentration in moles/litre	k lit.mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
Acetic acid 0.004	3.00
Triethanolamine 0.00025	0.57
Sodium acetate 0.0005	0.28
Perchloric acid 0.00058	99% reaction in 45 mins.
Perchloric acid 0.000058	76% reaction in 45 mins.
Without any added substances	30% reaction in 45 mins.

TABLE 2

Rate constants (k) for reaction between Mercuric acetate (a) and Methyl crotonate (b) in methanol at different temperatures and in presence of added substances

$$a = 0.01M-0.025M$$

$$b = 0.025M-0.05M$$

Temperature °C	k lit.mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
30	0.14
35	0.19
40	0.25
45	0.32

Temperature $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$

Added substances with concentration in moles/litre	k lit.mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
Acetic acid 0.0008	0.14
Acetic acid 0.0016	0.21
Sodium acetate 0.00022	0.034
Triethanolamine 0.00034	0.024
Perchloric acid 0.00055	84% reaction in 45 mins.
Without any added substances	25% reaction in 100 mins.

by the same logic it might be expected that in the methacrylic and cinnamic esters, the α -methyl and β -phenyl groups would also cause electron accession to the carbon-carbon double bond making it more susceptible towards methoxy-mercuration.

Comparing the relative reaction rates of the different types of the carbonyl compounds, the following observations may be noted. Crotonaldehyde reacts much faster than crotonic ester. Acrylic esters react at a reasonable rate but there is negligible reaction with acrylamide. There is also practically no reaction with benzalacetone although cinnamic ester reacts at a measurable rate. Thus, the reactivities of the different compounds towards oxy-mercuration are found to lie in the order :

Now, any of these groups, when bound to an ethylenic system, should act, on the whole, electronegatively, that is withdraw electrons, making the double bond less susceptible than an alkene to electrophilic attack. The relative electron-withdrawing mesomeric effects of the complete group lie in the order¹² :

Hence, for an electrophilic reaction, the reactivities of the olefinic substance may be expected to be in the inverse order. Strangely enough, the experimental observations are just the reverse.

It appears from Table 3 that activation energy lies in the order :

The frequency factor also lies in the same order. Thus the two factors appear to act in opposition and the observed rate reflects the resultant effect.

TABLE 3

Energy of activation (E), frequency factor (A) and entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) for reaction between Mercuric acetate and substituted olefins in methanol

Olefins	E k.cal.mole ⁻¹	A lit.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger (at 30°) cal.deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹
Crotonaldehyde	6.7	2.5×10^3	-45
Crotonaldehyde in methanol ethanol mixture (1 : 1)	8.7	2.0×10^4	-41
Methyl crotonate	10.6	1.0×10^5	-38
Methyl acrylate	9.0	3.3×10^3	-44
Methyl methacrylate	15.0	3.8×10^6	-30
Ethyl cinnamate	8.5	3.2×10^2	-49

For the cinnamic ester, the slightly smaller activation energy with respect to that for the acrylic ester may be associated with the electron-releasing effect of the phenyl group in the β -position. The low value of the frequency factor and hence a high negative value for the entropy of activation may also be considered to be in line with our expectations, since the bulky phenyl group should obstruct the attachment of the bulky acetoxymurcuric group, thereby causing a high degree of rigidity in the activated complex and hence a larger loss in entropy. It may be noted that for all the compounds studied, the entropy of activation has a large negative value. This, in general, may be correlated not only with the large bulk of the addendum, but may also be associated with an ionic intermediate, presumably a cyclic one. What is intriguing is the relative order of entropy of activation.

Again, the values of activation energy for the crotonic and unsubstituted acrylate respectively are not in conformity with the relative degree of electron accession to the double bond.

Although the observed results cannot be explained in terms of simple structural considerations, the apparent anomalies must not be regarded as anything exceptional. In the transition state, there have to be extra electron displacements accompanying the process of activation, in response to the specific electrical demands of the reaction centre. The activated complex is inaccessible to direct observation and nothing can be known about the specific effects which Ingold¹³ collectively terms as "polarisability effects". These are not present either in the initial (reactant) or the final (product) state, but occur only in the transition state, thereby influencing, in an unpredictable manner, the energy as well as the entropy of activation. This may well lead to a reversal of what should be expected on simple structural considerations, even when the mechanism of the reaction is believed to have been well established.

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